

DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE MARKETING STRATEGY IN AGRICULTURE

¹Musyeva Shoirazimovna, ²Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna

¹Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service Professor of Marketing Department

²Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service Associate Professor, Department of Marketing

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14177337>

Abstract. *In this matter, the improvement of the mechanism for evaluating the effectiveness of activities in reducing the cost of products in agricultural sector enterprises, increasing its competitiveness and increasing the volume of sales in the foreign and domestic markets, development strategy, receiving quality products from producers on the basis of a contract, cleaning, peeling, molding and The organization of export shipments in terms of z was considered.*

Keywords: *agriculture, agrarian sector, product, market, strategy, export, efficiency, diversification.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur masolada agrar tarmoq xo'jaliklarida mahsulot tannarxini kamaytirish, uning raqobatbardoshligi hamda tashqi va ichki bozorda sotish hajmini oshirishdagi faoliyati samaradorligini baholash mexanizmini takomillashtirish, rivojlanish strategiyasi, mahsulot etishtiruvchilardan shartnoma asosida sifatli mahsulotlar qabul qilish, ularni tozalash, sarxillash, qoliplash va o'z muddatlarida eksportga jo'natish ishlarini tashkil qilish ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Kaliti so'zlar: *qishloq xo'jaligi, agrar tarmoq, mahsulot, bozor, strategiya, eksport, samaradorlig, diversifikatsiyalash.*

Аннотация. *В данном вопросе необходимо снизить себестоимость продукции аграрных предприятий, усовершенствовать механизм оценки эффективности их деятельности, повышения их конкурентоспособности и объема продаж на внешнем и внутреннем рынке, стратегии развития, получения качественная продукция от производителей на основе контракта, очистка, была своевременно продумана организация упаковки, формовки и отгрузки на экспорт.*

Ключевые слова: *сельское хозяйство, аграрный сектор, продукт, рынок, стратегия, экспорт, эффективность, диверсификация.*

Introduction

Until now, the development of agriculture has been one of the most important priorities and will continue to be so. Because the effectiveness of agricultural production, ensuring the economic and food security of our country, increasing the material well-being of not only rural residents, but also the population of our country, the productivity of our land, which is our priceless wealth, is inextricably linked with regular improvement of its quality.

The sustainable development of the agricultural network of Uzbekistan largely depends on the effectiveness of innovative activities. As a result of the assimilation of innovations, the production base in agriculture is updated technologically, technically, and organizationally and economically. This, in turn, strengthens Uzbekistan's integration into the world market.

In the era of market economy, it is important to further develop the country's agrarian sector and produce quality products in this sector. Of course, several factors affect the production of more quality products and the development of the agricultural sector, one of such important factors is the competitiveness factor, of course, it is no secret that this factor plays an incomparable role, in particular, the main factor in the production of the agricultural sector it is necessary to study and

research the problems of priority development of network farms and increasing their competitiveness in the production of agricultural products. The solution to this problem largely depends on the development and implementation of complex methods of state regulation of agricultural production. However, in the conditions of limited resources, the development of agrarian sector farms is the main factor for their effective use, and further increasing their competitiveness is necessary for the development of the sector and the production of quality agricultural products.

Analysis of literature on the topic. There are several specific aspects related to the organization of marketing in construction practice, without considering them it is difficult to talk about effective marketing activities. In theoretical developments, it is stated that the uniqueness of the construction market must first be connected to the properties of the construction product. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of research on the country's investment attractiveness for enterprises and their practical application. Among them, Byvalsev, VA. Fedotov V. M. Kogotkova IZ, Mekhtieva A. YU. We can include famous scientists like Giovanna Naranjo, Eugenio Pellic, Víctor Yepes.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include I. Usmanov, YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others.

In this article, we found it necessary to touch on some of these issues. When talking about marketing in construction, first of all, it is necessary to focus on the tasks of marketing in this field, that is, to analyze the nature and main directions of marketing in investment-construction processes.

Also, based on the fact that issues related to risks in agrarian enterprises are one of the most important issues of the country, it is necessary to further expand regulatory and methodological provisions in accordance with market principles, taking into account the current situation in ensuring competitiveness.

The level of entrepreneurship is one of the main criteria for assessing the competitiveness of agricultural enterprises. The level of entrepreneurship directly depends on the level of income of entrepreneurship based on the demand and supply and prices formed in the market of agricultural goods. This also determines the level of competitiveness of agrarian sector farms by having different levels of productivity based on their specialization in the production of agricultural products.

Agrarian network of farms development strategy development, primarily due to the specific characteristics of agriculture agricultural sector natural and economic conditions of farms, specialization, directions of their activities and results according to differentiation and adaptation, different levels of using internal and external opportunities of different business systems depend on objective processes. From this point of view, it is appropriate to determine the development strategy of agrarian enterprises, the groups that describe their activities based on their situation in real conditions.

Being like this serves as a criterion for determining the strategy for the development of agrarian chain farms. In the conditions of liberalization and modernization of the current economy,

the selection of the development strategy of the agrarian sector enterprises based on the market conditions, which corresponds to the above-mentioned characteristics of the agrarian sector enterprises, shows that the level of full consideration of not only the theoretical but also the real conditions is high. provides. Therefore, this factor is important in the competitiveness and sustainable development of agrarian enterprises. Also, it is appropriate for the agrarian sector farms in this direction to choose a diversification strategy because they specialize in the production of products in the conditions of low competition in the area where they operate.

It is recommended to carry out and develop the regional growth strategy together with the cooperation development strategy for entrepreneurial type of agrarian sector farms. When choosing a regional strategy, they can specialize in growing a certain agricultural product and focus on it.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Implementation of the development strategy of agrarian chain farms requires, first of all, a certain amount of resources. That's why the level of agrarian sector farms' current resource availability, access to credit and investment plays an important role in the implementation of their chosen development strategy.

In the process of ongoing structural changes in agriculture, farmers and peasant farms were selected as the main forms of agricultural production organization. Implementation of measures to encourage the development of farms is an important factor in their sustainable and effective development.

Analysis and results. Depending on the type of economy and the level of development, the countries are mainly divided into economy specialized in the production of raw materials, industrial economy, post-industrial economy, mixed economy and countries based on innovation economy or knowledge economy.

Innovative economy is the most developed type of economy and an educated society is characteristic for it. Currently, various mechanisms and institutional structures, i.e. the national innovation system, are being formed for the wide introduction and effective use of scientific and technical achievements. Technological modernization of agriculture is one of the priorities in stabilization of agriculture. It is aimed at further improving the management of agricultural machinery enterprises, increasing their efficiency and profitability, modernizing production in the field, technical and technological re-equipment, organizing the production of modern, high-performance, competitive machinery and equipment for the agro-industrial complex in domestic and foreign markets. it is necessary to implement a uniform technical policy.

To prevent and mitigate the negative impact on the development of the country's agrarian sector, the development of the activities of agricultural and economic entities, ensuring their stable operation and the implementation of the following measures to increase the export potential are among the most urgent issues today:

- in order to ensure the competitiveness of manufactured products based on the requirements of the market price situation, to introduce measures to reduce production costs, to reduce the cost of products due to the rationalization of agro-technological processes;
- reduction of production costs in agrarian sector farms, itsimproving the mechanism for assessing the effectiveness of activities in increasing competitiveness and the volume of sales in the foreign and domestic markets;
- during the season, receiving high-quality products from producers on the basis of a

contract, organizing their cleaning, drying, molding and sending them for export on time, etc.

In the current period, it is appropriate to give priority to the following activities in the sustainable development of the agricultural industry of our country:

- further development of the work of infrastructure facilities serving agrarian chain farms;
- in order to provide the population with the main types of agricultural products at low prices and continuously, which buys, stores, transports and sells fruits and vegetables and grape products and potatoes from agrarian sector farms at reasonable prices to domestic consumer markets, establishment of specialized companies that carry out and finance exports and provide them with a sufficient amount of working capital and the necessary material and technical base;
- in order to prevent the negative consequences of the global food problem, optimization, from existing developed recommendations effective use and increase production efficiency.

Today, Uzbekistan has all the necessary socio-economic bases for deepening innovation processes and strengthening the innovation base. However, there are problems in the transition of the agricultural sector to the path of innovative development, or in other words, the implementation of innovative projects at the scale of one or even several farms, because: firstly, farms and processors of agricultural products slow participation of subjects in ordering scientific research works and funding research; secondly, the economic entity itself cannot carry out research and financing of scientific research in the development of advanced innovative technologies; thirdly, in order to use new technology and new varieties, producers and processors of agricultural products do not have enough knowledge, they need to use the services of scientists and specialists, and farmers face certain difficulties in processing and selling products; fourthly, there is insufficient demand from manufacturers for innovative developments prepared by scientists of higher education and scientific research institutions, there is no organic connection between them; fifth, the irresponsibility of some agricultural producers.

In the conditions of socio-economic changes taking place in the world and inter-country integration, it is necessary to move the agricultural network and the countryside, as well as the rural infrastructure, to a new innovative development path in the republic in a short period of time. Through this way, there will be an opportunity to increase the position of the village on a modern technical and technological basis.

Transitioning the economy of Uzbekistan to the path of innovative development is considered one of the priority tasks today. According to the analysis, the volume of innovations in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan is 1-2% of the total gross domestic product, and in the rural infrastructure network, this indicator is even less, although this indicator is 50-60% in other developed countries. is more than %.

The use of modern techniques and technologies in production creates the following opportunities:

- production of competitive products that meet the requirements of world friendship;
- the financial results of the enterprise will be higher due to the significant reduction of the product cost, and the opportunities will expand;
- saving raw materials and resources; reduction of negative impact on the environment, etc

If these techniques and technologies have an innovative character, that is, they are based on developments and ideas that have not been used in practice before, then the economic and social

importance of their use will be even higher. The implementation of innovative technologies in production allows to achieve higher efficiency compared to the technologies used in this field.

Conclusion

The international market of agricultural products is a very complex and diverse socio-economic system. The relations in it are greatly influenced by the abundance and uniqueness of the products, as well as the existence of interests of all countries. Entering the market of food products and occupying its place is one of the diseases of the development of the national economy.

Application of modern sales technologies in the export of fruit and vegetable products with high export potential in agriculture. For example, in the use of agrofranchising technology, it is possible to increase export opportunities by using the brand of Uzbekistan's products in local firms or large sales companies in the market.

We believe that the application of the above proposals will expand the export potential of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. PF-5853 "On approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030"
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2019 No. PF-5718 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of support and protection of entrepreneurial activity".
3. Resolution PQ-4525 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 20, 2019 "On measures to further improve the business environment in the country and improve the entrepreneurship support system".
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5057 dated 25.05.2017 on measures to further promote the export of local products and ensuring their competitiveness in foreign markets.
5. "On further improvement of the organization of farming activities in Uzbekistan and measures for its development" PF- No. 4478, 22.10.2012.
6. Olimzhanov O. and others. Basics of farming and organization of production. - T.: Sharq, 2003, -270 p.
7. Salimov B. and others. Economy of farms and peasant farms. - T.: TDIU, 2004, 124 p.
8. Umurzokov UP, Toshboyev AJ, Toshboyev AA Farm economy. - T.: ECONOMY - FINANCE, 2007. - 226 p.
9. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023
10. Musaeva Sh.A. Integrated marketing communication Study guide "Maharat" publishing house, Samarkand - 2022
11. Musaeva Sh.A., Usmonova DI Innovative marketing "TURON EDITION" study guide for 2021.